

Transformation of oil refinery sludge (ORS) into value-added compost with two epigeic earthworm species *Eisenia fetida* and *Eudrilus eugeniae*

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Vermicomposting has emerged as a feasible and environmentally clean bioremediation technology that utilizes the biodegradation potential of earthworms. Earthworms can expedite the decomposition and remediation of various organic and industrial wastes. The present study investigated the potential of transforming oil refinery sludge (ORS) into value-added compost using vermicomposting with two earthworm species, *Eisenia fetida* and *Eudrilus eugeniae*, and aerobic composting. Nine different compost batches consisting of six vermicomposting batches (EF₁, EF₂, EF₃, EE₁, EE₂, and EE₃) and three aerobic composting batches (AC₁, AC₂, and AC₃) were prepared with varying proportions of thermo-stabilized ORS substrate and farmyard manure (FYM). Compost samples from these nine compost batches were taken temporally (0th day, 45th day, and 90th day) in triplicate and analyzed for changes in their physicochemical parameters and metal concentrations. The compost produced from EE and EF vermicompost batches observed a higher reduction in bulk density and pH. Compost samples from AC₂ recorded a higher EC than the other compost batches. The vermicompost batches had a significant decrease in total organic carbon (TOC) content (%) and an increase in available NPK content. The concentration of heavy metals (Cr, Pb, and Cu) reduced significantly for the EE and EF batches compared to those from AC batches over the experimental period. Overall, compost produced from the vermicomposted batches (especially EE₂) showed the best results.

Keywords: Compost; vermicompost; earthworms; oil refinery sludge